

Design of fuzzy PID with filter controller for AGC of Thermal-Hydro Units

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Abstract

The automatic generation control (AGC) is significant process in present days power system. The present work deals, the ability of fuzzy PID controller with filter (PIDN) for AGC. At first, two area thermal-hydro system is designed in *s*-domain. It comprises of uncertainties like reheat turbine, time delay (TD), generation rate constraint (GRC) and governor dead band (GDB). In the next step, fuzzy PIDN controller is placed as a controller and its optimal parameters are chosen by optimizing with teaching learning based optimization (TLBO) technique. Further, the dominance of fuzzy PIDN controller is observed by comparing with PID and PIDN controllers. In the end, the effectiveness of proposed controller is observed by verifying its robustness and by applying pulse load.

Keywords: AGC; Fuzzy PIDN; GRC; GDB; TD; TLBO.

1. Introduction

In recent days, all the consumers are expecting to receive quality in power but it is complicated due to inequality between generation and load. Due to this, there will be oscillations in power system parameters (frequency and tie-line power) in the interconnected power system. The oscillations can be reduced by introduction of automatic generation control (AGC). The main function of AGC is to maintain frequencies in the areas and power flow in the tie-lines which are interconnected between the areas closer to their scheduled levels [1-3].

In past, researchers expressed their ideas in choosing secondary controller, optimization techniques for AGC problem [4-10]. The problem of AGC is designed with moth flame optimized PI-PDF controller and the authors [11] also presented its supremacy with other classical controllers. Khamari *et al.* [12] have proposed to employ modified moth swarm optimized fuzzy PD-PI for frequency regulation of hybrid power system. The authors also shown experimental results by using OPAL-RT based real time simulator. Differential Evolution based fuzzy PID controller was proposed by Chintu *et al.* [13] to reduce the deviations in frequency and also shown robustness of suggested technique. Revathi *et al.* [14] have proposed fuzzy gain scheduling technique for AGC problem and the results are validated with conventional PI controller. The authors [15] have considered uncertainties and employed GA to optimize the decentralized integral controller parameters to achieve better system performance. Karnavas and Papadopoulos [16] have proposed fuzzy logic and neural networks to control the system frequency and power output. Ahamed *et al.* [17] highlighted the potential of reinforcement learning approach to the AGC and explained how the problem of AGC in power systems can be formulated as a stochastic multistage decision problem to learn an AGC controller using a set of teaching data. Ghoshal [18] proposed a method of GA and Simulated Annealing (SA) by choosing a objective function which directly depends on transient performance. Having all, the present study includes TLBO-fuzzy PIDN controller for AGC task.